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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ADAV MOHAK GIRISH bearing the USN 5SU20PT801 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. AKSHITHA K R bearing the USN 5SU20PT802 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a manuscript for journal submission”** in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ASHWINI BHAT B bearing the USN 5SU20PT803 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. ASMITA KADEL bearing the USN 5SU20PT804 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a manuscript for journal submission”** in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. DAYMA NIKITA OMPRAKASH bearing the USN 5SU20PT805 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JADHAV MONALI SANJAY bearing the USN 5SU20PT806 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a manuscript for journal submission”** in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JISHA V R bearing the USN 5SU20PT807 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a manuscript for journal submission”** in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. JOSHI JAI KAILASH bearing the USN 5SU20PT808 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. MOKALE PRAMOD PRABHAKAR bearing the USN 5SU20PT809 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. NIKITHA bearing the USN 5SU20PT810 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a manuscript for journal submission”** in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PATEL DIVYA SANJAYBHAI bearing the USN 5SU20PT811 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. PATIL GANDHALI JAYKUMAR bearing the USN 5SU20PT812 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SAROJ KUMAR SAHOO bearing the USN 5SU20PT813 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHETTY NIDHI SADANAND bearing the USN 5SU20PT814 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHINE T bearing the USN 5SU20PT815 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a manuscript for journal submission”** in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHRAVAN KUMAR bearing the USN 5SU20PT816 has completed his/her mini project on “**Preparing a manuscript for journal submission**” in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SHREEJA K bearing the USN 5SU20PT817 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a manuscript for journal submission”** in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr./Ms. SOWMYA B bearing the USN 5SU20PT818 has completed his/her mini project on **“Preparing a manuscript for journal submission”** in the second year of the MPT programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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